

Spatial Entity Summarization & Comparison from Geospatial Knowledge Graphs

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Geospatial Knowledge Graphs (KGs) provide a compelling data model for representing complex spatial and temporal information including spatial entities and their many attributes. Recent examples include graphs such as KnowWhereGraph (KWG)[2], Urban Flooding Open Knowledge Network (UFOKN)[6] and WorldKG[1]. Strengthened by a well-built ontology, geospatial KGs can support semantic information organization that flexibly adapts to a range of information retrieval tasks beyond what a traditional database or Geographic Information System readily supports. Ontology design patterns for spatial, temporal, statistical and measurement information provide atomic data organization of the information and relevant entities. However the structure of these ontology design patterns, coupled with complex spatial relationships that may be either pre-materialized or computed at query time, make it difficult to compare information about places and to compute summaries of places. The KG structure supports computers semantically understanding data, however it may still be difficult for humans to perform knowledge discovery, inference, and exploration with the full graph structure due to the more limited information capacities of humans and visual displays. How then can we systematically decide the most important facts to present to the user interested in a particular context? The driving question of this research is to develop a method to summarize geospatial entities from a KG and to compute the key similarities and differences between two places represented as geospatial entities of the same type.

As a case study this research will use SAWGraph, which is a geospatial Knowledge Graph under construction that supports analysis of environmental contamination of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) especially as relating to food and water sources. This graph combines information about known sampling results, sites of known chemical releases, vulnerable features, environmental context and chemical informatics. The information has varying degrees of spatial resolution and accuracy, and many of the geospatial features have nested spatial relationships. Due to varying spatial resolutions of information, the main question is to summarize and compare information about places that represent spatial regions, such as towns or S2 cells. S2 cells are part of a hierarchical indexing structure, similar to web map tiles, that divides a spherical globe into nested cells based on geodesic lines [4]. In SAWGraph an S2 cell may contain numerous sampling sites, vulnerable water supply wells, and many other properties about the region such as hydrology and landcover that provide a signature of its specific environmental and social context. An example question in this use case that this research will seek to answer is: Why do these two places have different levels of contamination though biosolids from the same source were applied or though they are the same distance from a known contamination source? This will highlight the key similarities and differences between two regions of interest based on domain of interest.

To tackle Knowledge Graph place entity summarization and comparison the plan for the research is to take a multi-step approach that involves building subgraphs, simplifying, and then comparing two subgraphs. To achieve the comparison of two place entities, the project will investigate and compare different approaches that include shape comparison using SHACL, clustering techniques using graph embeddings, and pattern mining. Following the existing literature on entity summarization tasks [3] [5], there are some important considerations for

spatial entities that would need to influence the scoring of which facts about a location are more or less relevant to the specific use case. Additionally place descriptions often rely not only on direct attributes or contained entities, but also on important reference landmarks [7], such as nearby polluting facilities in the case of PFAS contamination which help describe the environmental context. The summary and comparison will facilitate inductive reasoning and further hypothesis testing about the difference between places in complex human and environmental systems.

References

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